

The Grane forest fire 2025 (site description, orthomosaics, metadata for TOMST TMS-loggers and soil sampling)

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To investigate post-fire dynamics in the Central European uplands, a long-term, multi-parameter monitoring programme is being conducted in the municipal forest of Goslar (Harz Mountains, Germany). The study aims to assess vegetation recovery, microclimatic conditions, and changes in soil properties at a wildfire site located at 450 m a.s.l. (51.904028° N, 10.392083° E), near the city of Goslar—a [UNESCO World Heritage region](#)—and upslope of the Granetal Reservoir.

The wildfire ignited on 22 June 2025 and was brought under control four days later, on 26 June 2025, affecting a total area of approximately 8 ha. The burned, drought-affected stands were predominantly composed of standing dead Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) trees resulting from bark beetle infestation. Beech, larch, and birch occurred as associated mixed tree species. In addition, the fire affected three reforestation areas with mixed tree species compositions:

1. *Fagus sylvatica*/*Pseudotsuga menziesii* with *Carpinus betulus*
2. *Fagus sylvatica*/*Pseudotsuga menziesii* with *Acer pseudoplatanus*
3. *Fagus sylvatica*/*Pseudotsuga menziesii*/*Acer pseudoplatanus*/*Quercus robur*

These reforestation areas were almost completely destroyed.

Monitoring began four days after the fire was extinguished (i.e., on 30 June 2025) and included soil and ash sampling as well as vegetation surveys conducted by researchers from the Landscape Geoscience Group, Institute of Geography, University of Göttingen. One week later, the first TOMST TMS 4 loggers were installed to measure surface and soil temperature as well as soil moisture.

Unoccupied aerial vehicles (UAVs) were used to characterize initial site conditions using optical and LiDAR sensors. UAV flights over the burn area were conducted on the 29.08.2025 during calm and practically cloud-free weather conditions. RGB imagery was acquired with a DJI Mavic 3 Enterprise UAV, multispectral reflectance data was captured using a DJI Matrice 300 RTK UAV equipped with a Micasense Altum camera. All images are acquired with forward and side overlap of 80% to ensure proper orthomosaic reconstruction using structure-from-motion. LiDAR scans were obtained with the YellowScan MapperPlus at 50% line overlap. All UAV data sets obtained RTK-based GNSS positioning data using active SAPOS connections. LiDAR data was post-processed using a SAPOS reference station. Flight heights were between 90-110 m above ground level and followed a SRTM terrain model to ensure constant elevation offset.

Acknowledgements

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Fig. 1: Burnt site on 02 June 2025, photos: Lea V. Deutsch.

Fig. 2: Images of UAV-flights by firefighters Goslar including thermal sensors (left), 26 June 2025, with Granetal reservoir in the background.

Fig. 3: RGB orthomosaic of the Grane forest fire (date: 29.08.2025). The extent of the burnt area was manually digitized.

Fig. 4: Location of TMS 4 TOMST dataloggers measuring since July 2025. Water areas to the left belong to the Granetal Reservoir.

Fig. 5: PlanetScope-based normalized burn ratio with 3 m spatial resolution. Negative values indicate higher burn severity.